

A New Rubber Modified Resin

H. Ishikawa, K. Naito, T. Honda

The Technical Center, Bridgestone Tire Co., Ltd., 2800-1, Ogawa Higashi-machi, Kodaira City, Tokyo 187, Japan

ABSTRACT

A new modified rubber, which had reactive (meth)acryloyloxy groups as pendants, was successfully prepared. The compound consisting of the modified rubber and various vinyl monomers was found to be suitable for a base resin of FRP products. One of the advantages of the resin is that the resin may contain high filler level. In other words, high glass content FRP, which results in improving mechanical strength, can be easily obtained. Thus the new rubber modified resin may be suitable for a base resin of FRP with high mechanical properties. The modified rubber in the resin plays an important role to improve toughness and impact resistance of the resin. Izod (notched) impact and drop-ball (2.27kg in weight) impact tests were used to examine the toughness of the new rubber modified resin.

INTRODUCTION

FRP products have found widespread applications due to their good overall mechanical properties. Recently, high flexural strength and impact resistance of FRP are required especially in the field of automobile industry.

Toughness of unsaturated polyester resins for FRP may be improved in a number of ways. One method is to incorporate rubbery additive.⁽¹⁾ When rubbery additives are mechanically mixed with unsaturated polyester resins, these rubbery additives usually are incompatible even in the liquid state, and separation readily occurs. Many attempts to introduce polar groups to rubber molecules have been performed for the purpose of improving the mutual compatibility of rubbery polymers and unsaturated polyester resins.

The present report describes our experience of improving the toughness of a resin which contains a modified rubber as a component. Several advantages have been found for the resin. First, the rubber modification was carried out in a relatively simple way. Second, the resin composed of modified rubber and vinyl monomers may contain much higher filler and glass levels than conventional unsaturated polyester resin.

EXPERIMENTAL

Resin Compound

Modification Of Rubber. An elastomer, which has unsaturated double bonds, was dissolved into styrene monomer. After adding methacrylic acid to the above solution, t-butyl hypochlorite was added dropwise at room temperature. Thus a

chlorohydrin ester of the elastomer was obtained. In this reaction, it was found that the t-butyl hypochlorite and methacrylic acid reacted with the elastomer predominantly. The resulting polymer solution was able to use for a base resin of FRP, without further purification.

In the reaction mentioned above the methacryloyloxy functional groups were introduced to the rubber as reactive pendants. (2), (3), (4)

In this paper the (meth)acryloyloxy modified rubber is referred to "MM-R (1/500)". In the parenthesis the fraction stands for the degree of modification, i.e., the numerator 1 is the mole number of the (meth)acrylic acid added and the denominator 500 is the weight (g) of the polymer respectively.

Compounding Of Resins. Typical compositions of MM-R base resin are shown in Table-1. All components were stirred vigorously in a flask. Calcium carbonate powder (CaCO₃) was added to the mixture in the same way. The ratio of the resin and CaCO₃ is shown in Table-2.

Preparation Of FRP Panels And Test Pieces

FRP Panels. All test panels were prepared by laminating the modified resin compounds and chopped glass strand mats alternately. Then the laminated compounds were cured at 140°C for 5 minutes in a 300x300x2 - 6mm mold using 100kg/cm² pressure. The curing agent was t-butyl peroxy benzoate used at 1-3 percent concentration.

Test Pieces. Test pieces for tensile and flexural properties were cut out from the cured panel according to JIS (Japanese Industrial Standards) K 6911. Test pieces for Izod (notched) impact test were prepared according to JIS K 7110, in this case a thicker panel (6mm) was used. For the drop-ball test larger panels (300x300x3mm in size) were used.

Experimental Methods

Infrared Spectroscopy. Experiments were carried out with a model IRA-3 spectrophotometer (Jasco). A thin film of the modified rubber on a KBr plate was prepared to take the transmission spectra.

Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Spectroscopy. A JNM-PS-100 NMR spectrometer (JEOL) was used for ¹³C-NMR studies.

Viscosities. Resin viscosities were measured at 20°C with using a Rheotron R-P3-1A viscometer (Seikikogyo Lab.) (at shear rate 30 sec⁻¹)

Compatibility. Compatibility of resins was observed 24 hrs after the resins had been mixed. The symbols in Table-3 stand for as follows.

- : Compatible
- △ : Partially Compatible
- × : Incompatible (Phase Separation)

Cure Time. Cure time were measured with using a du Pont DSC at 140°C isothermally.

Glass Contents. Glass contents were measured according to JIS K 6919.

Tensile And Flexural Properties. Tensile and flexural properties were measured according to JIS K 6911. (An Instron type testing machine was employed in the experiments. The cross head speeds were 5mm/min for tensile and 1mm/min for flexural properties respectively.)

Izod (Notched) Impact Tests. Izod (notched) tests were carried out according to JIS K 7110.

Drop-Ball Impact Tests. A steel ball (2.27kg in weight) fell from 3-5 m height and struck the FRP panel. (300x300, 3mm in thickness) The degree of damage and the radius of cracks were observed at the opposite side of the panel.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Characterization Of The Modified Rubber

Infrared and ^{13}C -NMR spectroscopies were used to examine the structure of the modified rubber. Infrared spectra are shown in Fig-1. The absorptions at 1720cm^{-1} and 1160cm^{-1} in IR spectrum were ascribed to C = O and C - O stretching vibrations of the methacryloyloxy group respectively. The new peaks at 75.0ppm and 62.8-63.2ppm observed in the ^{13}C -NMR spectrum (Fig-2) were assigned to the C atoms of the modified site of butadiene unit. The new other peaks were also assigned to the C atoms of the introduced methacryloyloxy group.

Uncured Resin Properties

Viscosities. The apparent viscosities of filler loaded MM-R base resin are shown in Table-2. It is clear that the viscosities of filler loaded MM-R resin are lower than those of conventional unsaturated polyester resin.

Compatibility And Cure Time. The compatibility of the MM-R base resin with a conventional unsaturated polyester resin was improved as the degree of modification of polymer increased. (Table-3) Generally, non polar rubber such as polybutadiene rubber is incompatible with an unsaturated polyester resin. Cure Time (time to complete the cure reaction) decreased remarkably as the degree of modification of rubber increased. (Table-3) When unmodified rubber was used in the resin, it took more than 30 minutes to finish the cure reaction. In the DSC measurements, the arrows show the end points of cure. (Fig-3) As one may expect, the reactive methacryloyloxy groups of the modified rubber probably react with vinyl monomers and contribute the acceleration of curing.

Laminate Panel Properties

Mechanical Properties. A typical set of laminate panel properties for MM-R base resin (recipe A, in Table-1) is shown in Table-4. It was found that the tensile and flexural properties of MM-R base resin were superior to those of conventional unsaturated polyester resin at the same glass content levels. These results are shown more clearly in Fig-4 and 5. For flexural strength, remarkable differences were observed at higher glass contents. Those results may be also attributed to the existence of reactive pendant groups of the modified rubber. The groups may copolymerize with vinyl monomers to give an uniform three dimensional crosslinked structure by a free radical reaction.

Izod (Notched) Impact Tests. Table-5 is a description of the impact resistances of laminates. The same results are shown in Fig-6 and 7. In those figures, it is clearly shown that the Izod values of MM-R base resin are higher than those of conventional unsaturated polyester resin at the same filler or glass content levels.

Drop-Ball Impact Tests. Izod impact test, as it is usually used, has some argument on its capability of reliably distinguishing toughness of ordinary FRP.

From this standpoint drop-ball impact test may be better measure of in-service impact resistance than Izod impact test. The results are shown in Table-5. In our experiments the results obtained by two different methods almost agreed.

CONCLUSION

Methacryloyloxy modified rubber was successfully prepared in various vinyl monomers in a relatively simple way. It was found that the solution may be suitable for a base resin of FRP. The mechanical properties of MM-R base resin laminate were superior to those of conventional unsaturated polyester resin laminate at room temperature. It was found that the flexural toughness, the Izod (notched) values and the results of drop-ball impact tests of FRP panels were remarkably improved by using MM-R base resin. The good mechanical properties of the modified resin are probably attributed to the existence of reactive methacryloyloxy groups of the rubber. The groups may copolymerize with various vinyl monomers to give an uniform three dimensional crosslinked tough resin.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors wish to thank Mr. Sugiyama and Miss Matsuyuki for the measurement of NMR spectra.

REFERENCES

- 1 Golemba, F., "A New Modified Rubber Additive to Improve Toughness of Unsaturated Polyesters", 35th Annual Technical Conference, RP/C, SPI, 5-A (1980).
- 2 Irwin, C.F. and Hennion, G.F., "Chlorination of Olefins in Reactive Solvents with t-Butyl Hypochlorite", J.Am.Chem.Soc., 63,858 (1941).
- 3 Winkler, D.E. and Hearne, G.W. "Reactions of t-Butyl Hypochlorite", J.Org.Chem., 25, 1835 (1960).
- 4 Honda, T., Japanese Published an Examined Patent Application No.84307/80

Table -1

Typical compositions of MM-R base resin

Component	MM-R base resin			
	(A)	(B)	(C)	(D)
MM-BR01 (1/500)	8.0			
MM-BR01 (1/250)		5.6		
MM-Solprene414 (1/1000)			28.9	
MM-BR01 (1/1000)				1.6
MM-B1000 (1/400)				53.4
Methacrylic acid	9.0	9.7	3.7	7.4
Styrene	72.5	76.0	67.4	27.6
TMPT	3.0	1.0		
Unsaturated polyester	7.5	7.7		

BR01 : Polybutadiene rubber (Japan Synthetic Rubber)
 Solprene414 : Radial block SBR (Phillips Chemical Company)
 B1000 : Liquid polybutadiene
 TMPT : Trimethylolpropane trimethacrylate

Table -2

Uncured resin properties

Component	Resin					
	MM-R base resin			Control		
Resin (%)	100	50	40	100	50	40
CaCO ₃ (%)	0	50	60	0	50	40
Viscosity (20°C , cps)	1000	12000	21000	1000	13000	45000

MM-R base resin : (A)
 Control : Unsaturated polyester

Table -3

Compatibility and Cure time

Component	8% MM-BR01 base resin		
	Unmodified	1/1000	1/500
MM-R base resin (%)	92.5	92.5	92.5
Unsaturated polyester (%)	7.5	7.5	7.5
Property			
Compatibility	×	△	○
Cure Time (min)	>30	10	5

Table - 4

Typical laminate properties

Component	Resin							
	MM-R base resin				Control			Ref.
Resin (%)	53.7	44.0	35.7	31.5	60.9	50.8	40.3	54.5
CaCO ₃ (%)	0	22.9	35.7	40.9	0	25.3	40.3	0
Glass (%)	46.3	34.1	28.6	27.6	39.1	23.9	19.4	45.5
<u>Property</u>								
Tensile strength (kg/mm ²)	17.5	15.7	12.7	12.2	14.3	9.1	8.2	9.5
Tensile modulus (kg/mm ²)	900	1000	1030	1170	990	800	960	890
Flexural strength (kg/mm ²)	44.0	30.3	25.2	23.3	25.0	18.5	16.8	19.8
Flexural modulus (kg/mm ²)	1090	1010	1010	1030	900	890	970	570

MM-R base resin : (A)
 Control : Unsaturated polyester
 Reference : Unmodified BR01 base resin

Table - 5

Impact resistances

Component	Resin					
	MM-R base resin			Control		
Resin (%)	54.0	43.4	35.5	54.5	51.0	41.3
CaCO ₃ (%)	0	21.7	35.5	0	25.4	41.3
Glass (%)	46.0	34.9	29.0	45.5	23.6	17.4
<u>Property</u>						
Izod impact (notched)(kgcm/cm)		69.8	59.2	81.4	39.1	32.0
Drop-ball impact height (m)	5.0	4.0	3.0	5.0	4.0	3.0
degree of damage	<i>no damaged</i>	<i>no damaged</i>	<i>no damaged</i>	<i>small</i>	<i>large</i>	<i>large</i>
radius of crack pattern (cm)	0	4.5	5.0	>5.0	15.0	>10.0

MM-R base resin : (A)
 Control : Unsaturated polyester

Fig-1 Infrared spectra of polybutadiene rubber (original and methacryloyloxy modified)

Fig-2 ^{13}C -NMR spectrum of methacryloyloxy modified radial block styrene-butadiene rubber (CDCl_3 , 200MHz)

Fig-3 Differential scanning calorimetry of resin compounds at 140°C isothermally

Fig-4 Relation between glass content and tensile strength

Fig-5 Relation between glass content and flexural strength

Fig-6 Relation between glass content and notched Izod value

Fig-7 Relation between calcium carbonate (CaCO₃) content and notched Izod value